

ANALYZING THE ACT OF CHILD STEALING AND BABY SELLING IN INDIA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THE STATES OF WEST BENGAL, JHARKHAND, AND ODISHA

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Abstract

One of the most upsetting crimes is stealing a baby. According to various authorized data, the number of cases of children being stolen and sold, child abduction, and child kidnapping has increased. As per various news reports, Child stealing occurs for a variety of reasons, including illegal adoption by hospital staff, prostitution, child rackets by various hospitals on the one hand, and poverty, which forces parents to sell their children, inability to pay medical bills, and women stealing baby boys to prevent fathers from remarrying after their son's death on the other. These kid racket teams operate by moving about impoverished areas, identifying pregnant ladies, persuading them with money, and then selling the infants. More than 122 million people in India lost their jobs in the first two months of the lockdown, according to research conducted by the Mumbai-based Centre for Economic Development. The majority (75%) of the group consisted of small

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dealers and day laborers. The tragedy was most felt by children as their jobless parents fled from abandoned cities and enterprises. Soon later, terrible claims about the buying and selling of children appeared. The present paper reviews the current status of child stealing in India with special reference to the state of Jharkhand, Odisha and West Bengal. Further, the paper highlights the problem of child stealing, kidnapping, abduction, selling and ways to detect and prevent it. The authors, through this paper, are trying to analyze the various issues raised before the Supreme Court & various High Courts in relation to child stealing and also trying to raise an alarm to drag government's attention towards increasing cases.

Keywords- Child Stealing, Baby Selling, Hospitals, Law, Judiciary

INTRODUCTION

Protecting children against exploitation of any type is a fundamental right for them.¹ During the past few years, numerous incidences of baby selling and child stealing from hospitals, child welfare, shelter homes, etc. have been reported in various print and electronic media reports, nationally and internationally. Even while many cases are documented, reported, and presented for trial before the court, many more go undetected. This is a very serious issue on which it is pertinent to draw the attention of the government and various agencies who have pledged to take care of the child's present and future. The various state governments are working hard to enact stricter and newer regulations, but their execution falls short of their intended goals. In order to maintain terror in the public's minds and deter serious crimes, the judiciary vigorously performs its duties by meting out severe punishment and dispensing justice. For the judiciary to deliver justice in a timely manner, much more work needs to be done. Additionally, fewer cases are being reported.

With particular emphasis on the states of Jharkhand, Odisha, and West Bengal, the purpose of the present research is to analyse the current situation of crimes committed in India against infants and children who require protection and care. Keeping this thing in mind, the research discusses the issue of child stealing, child trafficking, kidnapping, abduction, and baby selling as well as methods to identify and stop it. The current research paper has analyzed the roles and responsibilities of government and judiciary to prevent such crimes and to secure the end of justice for the victims of the said heinous crimes respectively. The purpose is to highlight the gravity of the issues and attract the attention of the organs of government towards the increasing number of cases relating to missing babies from hospitals and shelter homes and want them to consider giving victims justice

¹ Mr. Tim Cecil v. Unknown, (2011) 5 Mad LJ 209.

who are parents or guardians of children who require protection and care. Furthermore, the paper has discussed the most recent judicial rulings and directives to the executive branch on how to successfully implement the laws now in place.

WHO IS A 'CHILD'?

Children in India are defined as those under the age of fourteen by both the Constitution and the Census of India.² A boy or girl who has not attained the age of sixteen or eighteen is considered to be a "child" according to the statutory definition.³ Unless the age of majority is earlier under the relevant law, a child is defined under the 1989 United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) as anybody who is under the age of 18 years.⁴

HOW GRAVE THE ISSUE OF CHILD STEALING/BABY SELLING IS?

A. Survey Reports

In 2019, 1 billion children will be the victims of physical, sexual, or mental abuse worldwide, according to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020).⁵ Female victims of trafficking grew significantly between 2007 and 2017, according to The Counter-Trafficking Data Collaborative (CTDC), with the majority of them being trafficked for sexual exploitation and half of the victims being under the age of 26. According to the CTDC, victims between the ages of 15 and 17 make up the greatest category.⁶

² Dinesh Kumar, *Protection of Children Human Rights in India*, LEGAL SERVICE INDIA (July 26, 2022) available at <https://www.legalserviceindia.com/legal/article-11-protection-of-childrens-human-rights-in-india.html>

³ The Children Act, 1960, s. 2 (e)

⁴ Namita Chandwani, *Protection of Child Rights in India* 5 SUPREMO AMICUS 160 (2018).

⁵ *Violence Against Children*, WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION available at (July 26, 2022) <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/violence-against-children>

⁶ *Human Trafficking*, MIGRATION DATA PORTAL (July 26, 2022) available at <https://www.migrationdataportal.org/themes/human-trafficking>

Worldwide, sex trafficking affects 3.8 million individuals while 1 million minors are subjected to forced sexual exploitation, according to the International Labour Organization (ILO). During the same year, women and girls made up 99 percent of sexual exploitation victims.⁷ According to the ILO, Asia and the Pacific account for more than 70% of sex trafficking victims. Around 14% are from Europe and Central Asia, while 4% are from the Americas.⁸

The National Center for Missing and Exploited Children reports that children who run away frequently or for lengthy periods of time tend to be fleeing a dangerous setting or fleeing to an unsafe situation, according to statistics. In 2021, 1 in 6 of the more than 25,000 cases of missing children reported to NCMEC were probable victims of child sex trafficking. In 2021, child sex trafficking was probably the cause of 19% of the missing children reported to NCMEC who had fled child welfare custody.⁹

As far as Indian figures are concerned, more than one-third of India's population (i.e., 39%) is made up of children, while the rest is made up of adults (i.e. 61 percent).¹⁰ The following graph shows the percentage of children in each age group in the population. India has 472 million youngsters between the ages of 0 and 18 as per the 2011 Census. In 2020, 6.57 percent of Indians were above the

⁷ *Forced Labour, Modern Slavery And Human Trafficking*, INTERNATIONAL LABOUR ORGANIZATION (ILO) (July 26, 2022) available at <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/forced-labour/lang—en/index.htm>

⁸ *Child Labour And Migration (IPEC)*, INTERNATIONAL LABOUR ORGANIZATION (ILO) (July 26, 2022) available at https://www.ilo.org/ipecc/areas/Migration_and_CL/lang--en/index.htm

⁹ *Child Sex Trafficking*, NATIONAL CENTER FOR MISSING & EXPLOITED CHILDREN (July 26, 2022) available at <https://www.missingkids.org/theissues/trafficking>

¹⁰ *Children In India – Statistical Information*, TOY BANK (July 26, 2022) <https://toybank.in/children-in-india-statistical-information/>

age of 65, 67.27 percent of them were in the 15 to 64 age range, and roughly 26.16 percent of the population was under 14.¹¹

While there is no globally agreed definition of adolescence, the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) and the Government of India consider adolescents to be those aged 10 to 19 years in their decadal Census figures.¹² Around the globe, there are over 1.2 billion teenagers or about 16% of the total population.¹³

Moreover half of the world's teenagers reside in Asia. Based on data from the 2011 Census, India has more than 250 million adolescents, the highest number of any country on the planet. To put this figure in perspective, it outnumbers the population of 18 major Middle Eastern countries combined.¹⁴ As a result, the significance of adolescent development for India and its interconnection with the country's overall growth cannot be overstated.

It is difficult to find accurate trafficking statistics in such a large country as India, which has a population of 138 million people. Many occurrences go unreported and unidentified. Traffickers sneak thousands of children into India after having them kidnapped, sent to other nations, and then returned. A significant issue in India is the exploitation of people for the purposes of prostitution, sex trade, and other sorts of exploitation.

¹¹ *India : Age Distribution from 2010- 2020*, STATISTA (July 26, 2022) <https://www.statista.com/statistics/271315/age-distribution-in-india/>

¹² *UN Expert Group Meeting on Adolescents, Youth and Development*, UNITED NATIONS (July 26, 2022) available at <https://www.un.org/development/desa/pd/events/expert-group-meeting-adolescents-youth-and-development>

¹³ UNICEF DATA, *Investing in a safe, healthy and productive transition from childhood to adulthood is critical*, UNICEF.ORG (July 26, 2022) available at <https://data.unicef.org/topic/adolescents/overview/>

¹⁴ *Investing in Adolescent Development- A Case for India*, HINDUSTAN TIMES, (July 26, 2022) available at <https://www.hindustantimes.com/ht-insight/public-health/investing-in-adolescent-development-a-case-for-india-101638592002864.html>

There were 132426 offenses against children in 2018, according to the National Crime Record Bureau. There were 54 cases of juveniles being sold into prostitution and 98009 victims of child trafficking. Clarifications are still pending from the states of Sikkim, West Bengal, Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, and Meghalaya.¹⁵

The National Crime Record Bureau claims that, there were 139248 crimes against minors in 2019. In comparison to 2018, the number of crimes committed and recorded increased in 2019. 24 incidents involving child trafficking resulted in 96921 victims, and 28 of the victims were juveniles sold into prostitution. Clarifications from the state of West Bengal were still awaited in this data.¹⁶ Based on the National Crime Record Bureau, a total of 29,768 instances involving juveniles were reported in 2020, a drop of 7.8%.

With regard to kidnapping and abduction of minor children cases under Section 363 IPC in India in 2020, Maharashtra reported the most cases and victims of missing children, with 3867 and 3917 cases and victims, respectively, followed by Madhya Pradesh with 3686 and 3914 cases and victims, and Odisha with 3666 and 3666 cases and victims, respectively (See Table I). The states of Manipur and Mizoram had the fewest cases reported. For offences under section 366-A IPC, in 2020, Assam has the highest number of cases, victims, and crime rate of Procurement of Minor Girls, with 1052, 1055, and 8.7 respectively, followed by Haryana with 787, 789, and 8.6 respectively, and Jharkhand with 231,231 and 1.7 respectively (See Table II). The states of Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Goa, Mizoram, Nagaland, and Punjab had the fewest incidents reported. According to information provided by the National Crime Record Bureau there were no instances of the importation of girls from foreign countries under Section 366-B

¹⁵ Government of India, *Crime in India*, NATIONAL CRIME RECORDS BUREAU, 2019 (July 26, 2022) available at <https://ncrb.gov.in/en/crime-india>

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

IPC in 2020. For offences under sections 370 and 370-A IPC, Kerala, with 66 cases and a crime rate of 0.7, has the largest number of cases, victims, and crime rate of procurement of minor girls in 2020, followed by Jharkhand with 33, 40, and 0.2, and Assam with 32, 38, and 0.3 (See Table III). Arunachal Pradesh, Goa, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, and Sikkim all reported zero cases.

Madhya Pradesh has the most cases, victims, and crime rate per lakh population of selling of minors for prostitution under section 372 IPC with 4, 4 and 0.0, respectively, followed by Bihar with 3, 9 and 0.0, and West Bengal and Gujarat with 2, 2 and 0.0, respectively. Arunachal Pradesh, Goa, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, and Sikkim all reported zero cases. Madhya Pradesh also has the largest number of incidents, victims, and crimes involving the buying of minors for prostitution under section 373 IPC with 1, 1, and 0.0, respectively (See Table IV). There were no cases recorded in the other 27 states.

Jharkhand reported 250 incidences of child trafficking in all of its 26 districts in 2017, according to data released by the Ministry of Home Affairs. Palamu reported the highest number of incidents, with 50 girls and no boys being trafficked. Garhwa was next, with 43 incidents of girls being trafficked and zero cases of boys being trafficked (See Table V). In addition, Dhanbad reported 40 incidents of girls being trafficked but no cases of boys being trafficked. In 2017, the state of Odisha recorded 63 occurrences of adult and child trafficking though there was no data provided per district.

In West Bengal there were 298 cases of child trafficking across its 35 districts in 2017. The city of Kolkata saw the most cases, with 50 females and 2 boys being trafficked. The Diamond Harbour Police Department ranked second, with 41 cases of girls and no cases of boys being trafficked (See Table VI). In addition,

the Baruipur Police Department reported 25 cases of girl trafficking but no occurrences of boy trafficking. As Jharkhand did not provide data for 2018, data from 2017 were used in its place.

In 2018, the state of Odisha recorded 75 occurrences of adult and child trafficking. There was no data provided per district while there was a hike of almost 10 number of cases in 2018. There were 135 occurrences of child trafficking in 35 West Bengal districts in 2018, which is a significant decrease from the previous year. The city of Kolkata saw the most trafficking cases, with 63 girls and zero males. With 9 cases of girls and 9 cases of boys being trafficked, Mursidabad came in second. The Baruipur Police Department also recorded five incidents of girl trafficking but no incidences of boy trafficking (See Table VII).

MEDIA REPORTS IN WEST BENGAL, JHARKHAND, AND ODISHA

West Bengal

Thousand of babies have been trafficked from West Bengal to metropolitan cities Delhi and Mumbai using the modus operandi of agents covering the babies in teddy bear shaped boxes.¹⁷ Even persons who were running adoption centres and member of the state bureaucracy were arrested for trafficking newborn children in Salkia, West Bengal.¹⁸

According to the state CID stillbirths, over the past three years, two private hospitals in Baduria, North-24 Paraganas, have worked with an NGO to operate a substantial interstate baby trafficking network. Their tactic involved preying on single mothers and low-income parents and using fraudulent documents to sell

¹⁷ Shantanu Guha Ray, *Firstpost Investigation: Bengal's 'baby sale' racket saw 10,000 newborns sold in 20 years*, FIRSTPOST, (July 26, 2022) <https://www.firstpost.com/india/firstpost-investigation-bengals-baby-sale-trade-fuelled-by-doctor-agent-nexus-saw-10000-newborns-sold-in-20-years-3387864.html>

¹⁸ *10 Arrested From Bengal Adoption Centre For "Selling" Newborn Babies*, NDTV (July 26, 2022) <https://www.ndtv.com/india-news/10-arrested-from-bengal-adoption-centre-for-selling-newborn-babies-2618490>

their unwanted infants to childless couples. Even after tricking mothers into thinking they had delivered stillborn children, they have been known to smuggle infants. In connection with the racket, eight persons have been arrested, including two women.¹⁹

Chandana Chakraborty (55) and Sonali Mondal (30) were detained by the West Bengal Police Criminal Investigation Department (CID) in a separate instance of child smuggling, according to Nishat Pervez, DIG Operations. According to the authorities, the couple has sold more than a dozen babies in the last few years, not only in India but also outside India.²⁰

Jharkhand

The staff of a Missionaries of Charity shelter facility in this area sold a baby, and Chief Minister Raghubar Das has ordered the Jharkhand State Child Protection Commission (JSCPC) to inquire into the issue.²¹ At Nirmal Hriday, a Missionaries of Charity shelter home on Jail Road in this city, a female staff member and her sister were detained when it was claimed that they had sold a child born to a minor resident of the home to a couple from Uttar Pradesh.²²

An infant girl was abducted from a hospital in this area shortly after being born, and authorities eventually found and saved her after a 31-hour search. He asserted that the newborn was reportedly taken from the Shahid Nirmal Mahto Medical

¹⁹ Sweety Kumari, *West Bengal: CID Uncovers Newborn Trafficking Racket*, INDIAN EXPRESS, (July 26, 2022) <https://indianexpress.com/article/cities/kolkata/west-bengal-cid-uncovers-newborn-trafficking-racket-4390695/>

²⁰ Special Correspondent, "Two more held in baby smuggling racket", *The Hindu*, (27 February 2017)

²¹ PTI, *Jharkhand CM orders probe into selling of baby by staff of shelter home run by Missionaries of Charity*, TIMES OF INDIA, (July 26, 2022) <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/jharkhand-cm-orders-probe-into-selling-of-baby-by-staff-of-shelter-home-run-by-missionaries-of-charity/articleshow/64935772.cms>

²² *Ibid.*

College Hospital (SNMMCH) in the vicinity of the Saraidhela police station by two ladies and a little girl, who were all apprehended.²³

Three of the four kids who were allegedly sold by a Missionaries of Charity shelter house in Ranchi, a group established by Saint Teresa, have apparently been saved, according to Jharkhand Police. This rescue brings the total number of children in this case who have been saved to three. According to the Jharkhand Police, one of the suspects, Sister Konsalia, "admitted" to sending away the fourth kid and selling the other three for money.²⁴

Odisha

Several people in Rourkela were arrested on the basis of a complaint of offer for trafficking of a boy for Rs. 3 Lakh and Rs. 40,000 for a girl child.²⁵ In Jajpur, a father had to sell his minor daughter to repay of Rs. 5,000. The matter received attention of the police after the girl's grandfather reported to the police.²⁶ Childline, a NGO rescued a baby who was sold by his father who was a victim of drug

²³ *Newborn Stolen From Jharkhand Hospital Found, 3 Arrested: Police*, NDTV, (July 26, 2022) <https://www.ndtv.com/cities/newborn-stolen-from-dhanbad-hospital-found-3-apprehended-2583032>

²⁴ FP Staff, *Baby-Selling Racket In Ranchi: Jharkhand Police Claims Nun Confessed To Crime, Three Children Rescued So Far*, FIRSTPOST, (July 26, 2022) <https://www.firstpost.com/india/baby-selling-racket-in-ranchi-jharkhand-police-claims-nun-confessed-to-crime-three-children-rescued-so-far-4744411.html>

²⁵ IE Staff, *Child Trafficking Racket Busted In Rourkela, Seven Arrested*, THE NEW INDIAN EXPRESS, (July 26, 2022) available at <https://www.newindianexpress.com/states/odisha/2021/jul/27/child-trafficking-racket-busted-in-rourkela-sevenarrested-2335992.html>

²⁶ Mohammad Suffian, *Odisha Man Sells Minor Daughter To Repay Loan; Girl Rescued After Grandfather Lodges Fir*, INDIA TODAY (July 26, 2022) available at <https://www.indiatoday.in/crime/story/odisha-man-sells-minor-daughter-repay-debt-fir-lodged-1814545-2021-06-14>

addiction.²⁷ In Sambalpur a child was rescued from a couple who bought her for Rs. 15,000 from her destitute parents.²⁸

INTERNATIONAL FRAMEWORK TO PROTECT CHILDREN

Albert Thomas, Director of the International Labour Organization (ILO) stated that the evil... most painful to the human heart is the abuse of infancy". Serious effort in social law always starts with child protection. According to multiple reports, baby theft or minor stealing, selling, and buying are all on the rise. A lot of factors contribute to human trafficking, including a lack of opportunities, migration, sex tourism, and many others. Prostitution, money laundering, unpaid labour, organ harvesting, and other forms of trafficking are all prevalent factors for minor female children to be trafficked.²⁹ With regard to international provisions for protection of rights of children, the erstwhile League of Nations negotiated the Declaration of the Rights of the Child as the first international agreement on child rights.³⁰ Thereafter in 1989 the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), a binding international treaty, outlines the different rights guaranteed to every child without discrimination of race, religion, or physical ability. Governments are required to provide for the fundamental needs of children to reach their full potential.³¹ In 2000 two optional protocols

²⁷ *10-Day-Old Baby Allegedly Sold For ₹ 10,000 In Odisha, Rescued: Official*, NDTV (July 26, 2022) available at <https://www.ndtv.com/bhubaneshwar-news/10-day-old-baby-allegedly-sold-for-rs-10-000-in-odisha-rescued-official-2467897>

²⁸ Debabrata Mohanty, *Odisha police rescue one-month-old baby. She was sold for Rs 15,000*, HINDUSTAN TIMES (July 26, 2022) <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/odisha-police-rescue-one-month-old-baby-she-was-sold-for-rs-15-000/story-vaZJuHUrgzdBglo4awejiO.html>

²⁹ *Children shouldn't work in fields, but on dreams!*, EQUITY FOR CHILDREN - THE NEW SCHOOL (July 26, 2022) available at <http://equityforchildren.org/2019/06/children-shouldnt-work-in-fields-but-on-dreams/>

³⁰ Vaishali Tripathi, *Offences Against Children And Protection Of Their Rights* 8 AEGAEUM JOURNAL 784 (2020).

³¹ *UN Convention On The Rights Of The Child*, SAVE THE CHILDREN UK (July 26, 2022) <https://www.savethechildren.org.uk/what-we-do/childrens-rights/united-nations-convention-of-the-rights-of-the-child#!>

were drafted by the UNCRC. Non-enlistment of children in armed forces and prohibition on child prostitution and child slavery have been recommended in the protocols.³²

Article 1 of the Optional Protocol on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography 2000 forbids the sale of children which under Article 2(a) of the CRC Protocol is defined as any act or transaction in which a child is moved from one person or group of people to another for money or any other reason. Whether crimes are perpetrated locally or internationally on an individual or organized basis, Article 3 assures that this conduct (the selling of minors) is completely encompassed under criminal law. Governments are urged to take appropriate measures to prevent the sale of minors for any purpose under Article 35.

LEGAL PROVISIONS IN INDIA

Under the Indian Constitution children in India enjoy the same rights as adults of either gender as equal citizens, including the following rights: Equal rights are guaranteed under Article 14; the restriction against discrimination is guaranteed under Article 15; Article 21 guarantees the right to due process of law; Human trafficking and bonded labour are prohibited under Article 23. Articles 46 and 47 provides the right to protection against social injustice and all sorts of exploitation, as well as the right to adequate nourishment, a better standard of life, and improved public health.

The right to a free, obligatory basic education extends to all children between the ages of six and fourteen under Article 21-A. All children have the right to early childhood care and education up until the age of six under Article 45. A person is

³² *Optional Protocol to the Child's Rights Convention, concerning the sale of children, child prostitution and child pornography, 2000*, HUMANIUM (July 26, 2022) available at <https://www.humanium.org/en/protocol-child-sale/>

entitled to protection from any hazardous occupation until the age of 14 under Article 24 while Article 39(e) provides that everyone has the right to protection against mistreatment and being compelled into labor that is too physically demanding or taxing for them. Article 39(f) guarantees that children and young people will be protected from exploitation and moral and material abandonment.

As far as penal provisions are concerned, the IPC covers numerous offences which have been highlighted earlier. Specific offences also arise under the Immoral Trafficking Prevention Act 1956, Transplantation of Human Organ Act 1994, Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012 while procedures for children exist in the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) Act 2015 and the Commission for Protection of Child Rights Act 2005.

JUDICIAL RESPONSES

Baby theft or minor stealing, selling, and buying are all on the rise and are caused by a variety of factors including lack of economic opportunities, migration, sex tourism amongst others. Minor girls are commonly trafficked for a variety of reasons, including prostitution, money laundering, unpaid labour and organ harvesting. Courts have on several occasions intervened in the abovesaid situations.

In *Bachpan Bachao Andolan v. Union of India*³³ the petitioner encountered a number of children who had been forcibly detained and exploited in the circus, where they were subjected to sexual, physical, and emotional abuse. The Hon'ble Supreme Court issued a set of instructions for children who worked in circuses, stating that the government is well aware of the problem and has a thorough understanding of how many children labour in circus acts. In *Dr. Santosh Kumar Samanta v. Unknown*³⁴ the Calcutta High Court dealt with trafficking and sale of

³³ *Bachpan Bachao Andolan v. Union of India & Ors.*, (2011) 5 SCC 1.

³⁴ *In re, Dr. Santosh Kumar Samanta*, 2017 SCC Online Cal 7974.

newborn babies for large sums of money, which is illegal under both the Juvenile Justice Act 2015 and the Indian Penal Code, as well as in violation of the fundamental rights set out in Article 23. In the case of *In re Debasish Chanda*³⁵ the Calcutta High Court noted that the petitioner is a physician and a member of the Child Welfare Committee and there is evidence that he arranged for the delivery of babies from unwed mothers and/or women from economically disadvantaged backgrounds. He deceitfully separated these children from their biological parents by stating that they died during childbirth. Following that, the children were sold to other people for illegal adoption. The High Court of Punjab & Haryana at Chandigarh in *Madhu Bala vs State of Punjab*³⁶ opined that it is important to recall that the moment when the sale occurs is key in evaluating a person's responsibility under Section 372 IPC. At that point, the intent of the accused who sells the child must be considered.

In *State of Madhya Pradesh vs Dr. P.K. Jain*³⁷ the Court opined that the accused, in collusion with other hospital staff were selling newly born babies of unwed mothers from the hospital, and were caught red-handed while selling newly born child of an unwed mother in their hospital. The Court opined that the threat of minors being utilized for illegal and immoral purposes is all too well known in this country. Doctors in nursing homes who sell a recently born kid without ascertaining sufficiently the reason for which the child is being brought in are presumed to have knowledge that the child will be employed or exploited for an unlawful purpose at some point in the future. In *Smt. Nirmala And Anr vs The State*³⁸ it was alleged that the accused Doctor had made it a practice to sell destitute babies by preparing false documents. She illegally sold two babies with a false endorsement. *In Re: An Application for Bail v. Dr. Dilip Ghosh @ Dilip*

³⁵ Debasish Chanda, In re, 2019 SCC OnLine Cal 3275.

³⁶ *Madhu Bala v. State of Punjab*, (2011) CRA-S-3361-SB-2011.

³⁷ *State Of Madhya Pradesh v. Dr. P.K. Jain And Ors.*, (2005) CriLJ 877.

³⁸ *Smt. Nirmala And Anr v. The State*, Criminal Petition No.200150/2018.

*Kumar*³⁹ the anticipatory bail application was rejected on the ground that this is a case of trading in newborn babies for monetary gain.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Judicial opinion has helped a lot in addressing the issue but no major directions/guidelines have been issued for the executive to perform. Among all, only Delhi High Court⁴⁰ has taken pain to issue the directions with a view to streamlining the functioning of Delhi Police /Anti- Human Trafficking Units (AHTUs) in matters pertaining to tracing missing children.
- Strict byelaws are needed to regulate the functioning of the hospital personnel at all levels.
- All maternity hospitals must come under the strict scrutiny by medical boards and police/women and child development officers of the state.
- Various awareness programs shall be conducted by state governments in order to bring sensitivity towards issues pertaining to offenses against newborn and infants.

CONCLUSION

Childhood has been popularly understood as a "golden era" associated with simplicity, happiness, pleasure, fun, and the like around the universe. It is a time when the responsibilities of adult life, obligations, and duties are not present. Notwithstanding the best efforts of the government, a considerable percentage of children are victims of different types of maltreatment and trafficking. Child stealing, both nationally and internationally, is a problem of national safety and security, and as such, it is a nationwide problem that must be examined and tracked at the grassroots level within the country. Although judicial opinion has greatly aided in resolving the problem, the executive

³⁹ In Re: An Application for Bail v. Dr. Dilip Ghosh @ Dilip Kumar, CRM 5661 of 2017.

⁴⁰ Surender Sah v. State, (2020) SCC OnLine Del 466.

administration has yet to receive any significant instructions or recommendations. State medical boards, police, and child development inspectors should conduct thorough inspections of all maternity hospitals. The future prosperity of a society depends on how its children fare as they grow and develop, making children a “supremely significant national asset.” For a child to fully develop its individuality, the state must take care of it. Thus, the state must implement a number of awareness campaigns to increase awareness of crimes against newborns and babies. Every action made by a single person to prevent such heinous atrocities would save millions of lives, and it is critical to effect change and make sure that our "future flag bearers" have a secure and safe environment to grow in.

TABLE I
CASES OF KIDNAPPING AND ABDUCTION (S. 363 IPC)
(Missing Children Deemed as Kidnapped)

State	No. Of Cases	No. Of Victims
JHARKHAND	40	40
ODISHA	3666	3666
WEST BENGAL	1289	1291

Source: National Crime Records Bureau, ‘Crime in India 2020’

TABLE II
CASES OF PROCURATION OF MINOR GIRLS (S. 366A IPC)

State	No. Of Cases	No. Of Victims	Crime rate (per lakh population)
JHARKHAND	231	231	1.2
ODISHA	10	10	0
WEST BENGAL	30	30	0.1

Source: National Crime Records Bureau, 'Crime in India 2020'

TABLE III
**CASES OF HUMAN TRAFFICKING (Ss. 370 & 370A IPC) (Children
only)**

State	No. Of Cases	No. Of Victims	Crime rate (per lakh population)
JHARKHAND	33	40	0.2
ODISHA	15	17	0.1
WEST BENGAL	10	21	0.0

Source: National Crime Records Bureau, 'Crime in India 2020'

TABLE IV
CASES OF BUYING OF MINORS (S. 373 IPC)

State	No. Of Cases	No. Of Victims	Crime rate (per lakh population)
JHARKHAND	0	0	0
ODISHA	0	0	0
WEST BENGAL	0	0	0

Source: National Crime Records Bureau, 'Crime in India 2020'

TABLE V
MOST CHILD TRAFFICKING CASES DATA
IN JHARKHAND DISTRICTS (2017)

District Name	Boys Trafficked (Exclusive)	Girls Trafficked (Exclusive)	Total Children Trafficked
Dhanbad	0	40	40
Garhwa	0	43	43
Palamu	0	50	50

Source: Government of India, Ministry of Home Affairs, Reply to Unstarred Question No. 391, Lok Sabha, 17th March 2020

TABLE VI
MOST CHILD TRAFFICKING CASES DATA
IN WEST BENGAL DISTRICTS (2017)

District Name	Boys Trafficked (Exclusive)	Girls Trafficked (Exclusive)	Total Children Trafficked
Baruipur Police	0	25	25
Diamond Harbour Police	0	41	41
Kolkata	2	50	52

Source: Government of India, Ministry of Home Affairs, Reply to Unstarred Question No. 391, Lok Sabha, 17th March 2020

TABLE VII
MOST CHILD TRAFFICKING CASES DATA
IN WEST BENGAL DISTRICTS (2018)

District Name	Boys Trafficked (Exclusive)	Girls Trafficked (Exclusive)	Total Children Trafficked
Kolkata	0	63	63
Murshidabad	0	9	9
Purab Medinipur	0	7	7

Source: Government of India, Ministry of Home Affairs, Reply to Unstarred Question No. 391, Lok Sabha, 17th March 2020